

RUSSIAN AGGRESSION AND EXISTENTIAL CHALLENGES OF THE MODERN WORLD: UKRAINIAN CONTEXT

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The article examines issues related to the existential challenges of the modern world in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. The emphasis is placed on the consistency and insidiousness of the use of methods and forms of influence in the introduction of imperial narratives that are directed not only against the Ukrainian identity, the sovereign right of the Ukrainian people to have its own state, but also against the entire civilized world. According to the researchers, this was largely due to complacency of democratic countries with the liberal democracy achievements, the existing confidence in the benefits of the acquired economic stability and the inexpediency of major wars in modern conditions. The current state of Russian society, bellicose Russian diplomacy and the aggressive policy of the Russian leadership contradict the existing basic European values and democratic freedoms. The scenario of Russia's disintegration into separate independent states, which would deprive it of its imperial status and reduce its aggressive potential, is crucial for improving the political situation in the world and ensuring Ukraine's own strategic security. In this way, the entire civilized world will be liberated from the permanent threat of a new war which will have a positive impact on creating the necessary conditions for Ukraine's political and economic development in the context of building a sovereign European state.

Keywords: Ukrainian identity, democratic values, Russian imperial policy, international assistance, existential challenges

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Introduction

The recent events related to the Russian-Ukrainian war have actualized a number of issues that reflect the current political situation in Europe and the world.

The Russian aggression has demonstrated a threat not only to the Ukrainian people but also to the peoples of other countries and has influenced the stability and sustainability of political, economic, and cultural relations. The war mentality that penetrates both the Russian government and Russian society contradicts basic European values and democratic freedoms, and thus, there is little hope for democratic changes in Russia under the current Russian political leadership. The destruction of the empire as an expected outcome of the Russian-Ukrainian confrontation will create conditions for peaceful development on the continent and in the world as a whole, promote democratic changes in other countries and finally provide the necessary conditions for Ukraine's political and economic development.

Materials and Methods

Modern Western scientific research pays considerable attention, among other things, to the analysis of the policy of appeasement of the aggressor, Russia's past and present imperial policy and its totalitarian heritage in the context of studying the development of human civilization. Among others, we would like to highlight the well-known works by T. Snyder, A. Bezanson, Z. Brzezinski, G. Kissinger, F. Fukuyama, E. Applebaum, N. Ferguson, L. Middelaar, J. Lieber, and others. Characterizing the current situation, the research focuses on the analysis of Russian hostility that has developed historically because, as George Kissinger rightly notes, "global Russian imperialism was paradoxically combined with vulnerability as if the victorious march across half the world had created more potential enemies than security. From this point of view, the tsarist empire could be said to have expanded because it was easier to continue than to stop" (Kissinger, 2017). Another researcher, T. Snyder, focuses on the fact that "an imperial power does not recognize political formations that stand in its way and which it considers colonial territories so it destroys and sabotages them, claiming that they have never existed." (Snyder, 2020). According to A. Bezanson, European attempts to perceive Russia "through a deformed prism" (Bezanson, 2017) have resulted in new existential shocks that the civilized world has experienced in the twenty-first century.

In addition, according to Z. Brzezinski, "the emergence of an independent Ukrainian state not only forced all Russians to rethink the nature of their own political and ethnic identity but also became a significant geopolitical failure for the Russian state" (Brzezinski, 2022). This, of course, was not something its political leadership could accept. For the Ukrainian people, as for the most individuals in the world, the nation remains, according to F. Fukuyama, the largest unit of solidarity to which they instinctively feel loyalty and which becomes a critical pillar of the state's legitimacy (Herasymchuk, 2023) which is confirmed by the nature of Ukrainian resistance to Russian aggression.

In this context the research of domestic scholars such as S. Plokyh, S. Vidnyansky, Y. Vermenych, L. Yakubova, T. Herasymchuk, O. Yas, O. Kondratenko, A. Kyrydon, S. Troyan, and others is of great importance. We should agree with Y. Vermenych's statement that "to a large extent, the conflict-military dimension of the Ukrainian historical development is programmed by the condition of prolonged dependence and statelessness" (Vermenych, 2023). The researchers are of the opinion that Russian aggression against Ukraine not only threatens the security and territorial integrity of Ukraine but also has a broader impact on European stability and threats to the sustainable development of Europe and the world.

Special attention should be paid to scientific works prepared by Ukrainian scholars on the eve of and in the conditions of the full-scale Russian aggression against Ukraine. It is worth paying attention to the monographic studies by S. Vidnyansky, A. Martynov, O. Kondratenko, "Ukraine in the History of Europe in the 20th and 21st Century", "Ukrainian Society in the Time of War", as well as to the informative work by S. Plokyh "The Russian-Ukrainian War: The Return of History".

In particular, the latter study emphasizes that "Ukrainian democracy posed a serious threat to the Russian political regime as it was an example of a political system with a strong parliament, encouraging and strengthening the Russian liberal opposition to the increasingly authoritarian regime in Moscow" (Plokyh, 2023). The panic of the Russian leadership was due not least to the continued production of political leaders committed to the idea of independence, their attitude toward Russia as a hostile country (Plokyh, 2023).

According to S. Plokyh, we are currently witnessing the determination of the Western democratic alliance led by the United States "...to eliminate the Russian threat to peace not only in

Ukraine but also in the whole world, ensuring Russia's defeat in the current war and reducing its ability to wage war in the future" (Plokyh, 2023).

The breakdown of the international legal order, economic crises, political and financial instability, violations of human rights and freedoms and the maturation of imperial resentment in Russia itself became a decisive factor in the escalation and unleashing of full-scale aggression against the Ukrainian people. Through its heroic resistance, Ukraine has significantly influenced regional and global processes in the world, demonstrating its commitment to protecting democratic freedoms and universal values.

The purpose of the article is to provide a comprehensive study of the existential challenges in the world which are fueled by the Russian-Ukrainian war and directly affect the spread of the geography of local threats and risks that could turn large-scale conflict situations into a third world war. Methodological basis of the study was based on the methods of historicism, extrapolation and comparative analysis. This has made it possible to study the main trends in the formation of the modern Russian imperial policy and the readiness of the Russian leadership to exploit the existing political instability in Europe and the world. Along with other methods, they have contributed to a comprehensive analysis of political relations between Ukraine and international organizations, in particular the European Union and NATO, on the path to joining and integrating into a collective system of political, economic, and military security. Methodological basis of the study was strengthened by identifying key aspects of international politics. It was important to outline the significant components of the crisis shifts that led to full-scale aggression and threaten the stability, security and sustainable development of democratic countries acquired European values and to study the geopolitical factors that influence the process of transformation of the country's modern social development. The originality and relevance of the study are enhanced by a thorough analysis of the changes that took place during the full-scale Russian aggression and the Ukrainian people's struggle for freedom and independence in the context of the chosen strategy of political interaction between Ukraine and the Western democratic alliance, which is a sign of the latest systematic research on this topic.

Results and Discussion

At the beginning of the twenty-first century, it seemed that the world had made a choice in favor of liberal democracy and had acquired the necessary political stability which was facilitated by a number of approved international treaties, agreements and decisions aimed at observing and preserving the existing legal order, the strategy of deterrence and balances.

The differences that persisted between both leading and small countries in the context of global problems of our time did not significantly affect the ability to find a compromise and consensus ways for the sake of peaceful development. Agreements on the approved borders according to postwar international acts, even in the conditions of rejection of certain final documents, were considered much more important and crucial in terms of the possible threat of new military conflicts and wars. For a certain period of time the Western world, following a policy with the "blinders on", neglected the historical lessons of the past. It illusively relied on the principle of "business as usual" and strong transnational economic ties that make major wars impossible due to economic inexpediency" (Bushuyev, 2023), and, in addition, it ignored the truth of the statement that "when a dictator, not a democratic leader, comes to power, the probability increases that he will lead the country to war" (Ferguson, 2017). In particular, the well-known political scientist S. Huntington while preferring to

preserve Euro-Atlantic solidarity as a determining factor in the existence of Western civilization, nevertheless, considered the risks of a Russian-Ukrainian war to be minimal.

At the same time the refined manners of the Russian elite could hardly hide original essence of this culture incomprehensible to the democratic world (Kissinger, 2017). In addition, the erroneous perception of Russia as a too powerful state without which it is impossible to build international relations has led to the fact that "the policy strategy of Western European countries towards independent Ukraine was somehow affected by certain features related to their past, that is, the historical factor" (Vidnyansky, 2020).

Unwillingness and inability to recognize "absolute evil" together with the policy of appeasement of the aggressor which has started more wars than any other modern great state (Kissinger, 2017) contributed to a fundamentally opposite result which affected the growth of tensions in international relations and led to military escalation in resolving existing contradictions between different countries.

The events of the late 20th - early 21st century associated with Russia's aggression against Moldova (1992), Georgia (2008) and Ukraine (2014) were accompanied by the seizure of sovereign territories of these countries. This state of affairs called into question the existing achievements of the world in terms of political stability when the international legal order was essentially broken, and the claims of some political leaders of leading countries to play a decisive role in fateful events were not confirmed. The Russian invasion of Ukraine was a reality check for the European Union and the United States. For many Europeans and Americans it turned out to be easier to listen to the ghosts of Russian propaganda than to defend the rule of law (Snyder, 2020). Aggressor's actions revealed "the current crisis of the European security system, the strategic carelessness and geopolitical inaction of the European Union (Middelaar van L, 2021). The leaders of NATO countries and leading European politicians also bear their responsibility for weakening the security situation and preventing a full-scale war in Europe" (Kyrydon, et al.,2023). How can we not mention that in the early twenty-first century Ukraine had serious grounds to join the European and transatlantic security systems, to become a member of the European Union due to the professing and observance of democratic values in Ukrainian society, and the reforms and changes that had been initiated? Unfortunately, these expectations were not realized (Brzezinski, 2022).

The EU's foreign policy was too moderate to, for example, "protect the Ukrainian Crimea from the Russian grip by deploying European ground forces or warships there which was paid for dearly" (Middelaar van L,2021).

Great conventional war unleashed by Russia in 2022 against Ukraine has finally removed from the agenda the question of having effective security guarantees provided by international organizations such as the UN, OSCE, the International Red Cross and other human rights organizations regarding the observance of the basic provisions of sovereignty and territorial integrity. At the same time, the outbreak of war demonstrated the maniacal determination of the Russian authorities to destroy Ukrainian statehood and the Ukrainian nation which was in line with the doctrines and narratives of the "russkiy mir" that had been put forward in advance (Minosian et al., 2023). What has been cultivated in Russian society for many centuries - the introduction of hatred, cruelty, lack of morality and humanity- has happened. Existential threats against Ukrainians were actually confirmed by large-scale killings, torture, rape of civilians and prisoners of war, acts of genocide in the form of abduction of Ukrainian children, etc. This gave reason to consider "the scale of the extreme, critical, traumatic experience gained by Ukrainians, especially after the full-scale

invasion on February 24, 2022, tectonic" (Yas, 2023). In fact, there was a "military conflict of the highest order between societies of different mentality, cultural orientation, collective memory, traditions, etc." (Kyrydon, 2024).

Considering the war against Ukraine as an act of self-preservation of its own country and nation because "imperialism is the very dominant feature of Russian consciousness without which its apologists cannot imagine the existence of their own state" (Vermenych, 2023). Russia has taken as a basis the constant expansion of its territorial possessions by forcible annexation of other lands. It was not a unitary state but was essentially a bulky empire that included different regions, religions, traditions and cultures, social groups and proto-national entities (Liber, & George, 2019). By doing so, Russia has effectively destroyed the previous international agreements and commitments made after 1991 in relation to the former Soviet republics.

The internal problems of the Russian regime with its attempts to restore the country's imaginary greatness, its desire to play a leading role in the modern world and its "own exceptionalism that has turned it into an anti-European state" (Bushuyev, 2023) have become even more apparent in the context of the ongoing aggression.

At the same time, the existential threat has become quite real for Europe itself, especially the Baltic states, as well as Poland and Finland, not to mention Moldova and Georgia. This has led to an increase in NATO's political activity as a bloc designed to play a stabilizing role on the European continent and in the world as a whole and its readiness to respond to global threats and existential challenges in the current situation.

Even during the war itself, the world has had the opportunity to see how individual local conflicts of varying magnitude are fueled and influence the situation as a whole. The renewal of the Arab-Israeli conflict, the Armenian-Azerbaijani war, the military activity of North Korea and Iran, their cooperation in creating joint programs with Russia, resolution of the conflict in Yemen, tensions over Taiwan, and China's increasingly bellicose rhetoric have caused a chain reaction that threatens the outbreak of World War III and the existence of human civilization. Russia is also pushing certain legal subjects to escalate in order to complicate the actions of the United States which has a responsibility to protect the countries of the conditional South.

Today, as in the past, it is easy to trace Russia's connection to most of the crises, terrorist attacks, revolutions and wars that periodically occur in the world. Having turned into a troubled nation-state, deprived of easy geographical access to the outside world, it remains potentially vulnerable to exhausting conflicts with its neighbors on the western, southern and eastern flanks (Brzezinski, 2022). It created political chaos that led to mass migration, loosening of borders, aggravation of the food problem and distraction of Western leaders to additional large-scale financial investments for the sake of security and protection of their own countries.

The activities of Marxist and socialist organizations, the revival of ideas of radicalism, leftism, sharp criticism of Western democratic values, liberalism as a fundamental importance of equal rights of the individual, law and freedom have become no less threatening in the twenty-first century with the active participation and mediation of Russian authoritarianism (Fukuyama, 2023). All of this is directly related to the weakening of the global political system, the decline of confidence in democratic institutions and the growing division of societies. This practice is already yielding negative results in terms of promoting certain candidates to leadership positions in different countries who are loyal to the perception of Russian narratives about the return of the multipolar world doctrine. The results of recent elections in some countries, even those that are members of the European Union

and NATO, show that "given the right conditions, any society can rebel against democracy" (Applebaum, 2023). That is why even the oldest and most reliable democracies are not immune to the growing popularity of political parties that use authoritarian language and symbols (Applebaum, 2023).

The growing political influence of such countries as China, Turkey, and Azerbaijan (Kondratenko, 2023) demonstrates the enduring popularity of authoritarianism as a form of government. This creates a real threat to established global democratic values which are based on the understanding of liberal restrictions on power as political insurance, effective and balanced use of the system of checks and balances (Snyder, 2021) while "the refusal to limit power in general is not always a dangerous proposal because it is not known who will lead the country in the future" (Snyder, 2021).

Complications also arise from internal problems as seen in the current political situation in the United States. There is a growing populist reaction to world events and the need to develop a winning strategy during elections is becoming increasingly apparent. This statement suggests that encouraging rhetoric does not always coincide with the preservation of impeccable liberalism and the steadfastness of democratic principles as has been observed during the term of Donald Trump.

"Russian armed aggression has become a bifurcation point in international relations leading to decisive political decisions and actions aimed at fulfilling the historic mission of uniting Europe which since the proclamation of the Schuman Declaration has been implemented as a "project of peace, democracy and freedom" (Herasymchuk, 2023).

Titanic efforts of the leaders of the leading democratic countries of Europe and the United States are now being met with radical statements and behavior of some politicians. They are hinting at the possibility of returning to the revision of existing borders in connection with the annexation of certain territories in case of Ukraine's possible defeat in the war with Russia. Such an inability to deal with the legacy of the past (Applebaum, 2023), the opposition of national subjectivity to European solidarity, does not contribute to internal unity, even in organizations such as the EU and NATO. In addition, there is a lack of unity in the assessment of global challenges, a lack of determination in making decisions that can have an impact on dictatorships in certain countries that are not known for their compliance with the norms and laws of the civilized world. According to Fukuyama, "young people are not grateful to the EU for peace and prosperity but they are irritated by its petty bureaucratic demands" (Fukuyama, 2023) which in the current situation can have disastrous consequences.

For a long time the Western world has reacted rather selfishly to the problems of the Global South in terms of providing political support, necessary economic assistance, financial restructuring, overcoming the effects of global warming, epidemiological situations such as COVID-19, etc. All this affects the situation when countries with about 2/3 of the world's population are in no hurry to impose sanctions against Russia. This does not prevent them from receiving food aid from Ukraine.

Without any doubt, the present reality shows that the whole democratic world slowly understands the existing threat of Russian aggression against the sovereign country like Ukraine for the further development of human civilization. "Despite the nuances of national positions (Austria, Hungary) on the duration and quality of support for Ukraine, the brutality of the challenge to all the values of European liberal democracy has revived the EU's common foreign policy" (Martynov, 2023).

“The current search for world order requires a coherent strategy to create a concept of order within different regions and to link these regional orders... If one country dominates militarily in a region and this leads to the establishment of order, then a crisis can arise in the whole world” (Kissinger, 2017). The fact that “the triumph of universal principles must be accompanied by the recognition of the reality of the history and culture of other regions” should not be underestimated (Kissinger, 2017). Dynamics of changing attitudes related to the unleashed war is quite indicative of strengthening support for our country, taking responsible decisions that should have a positive impact on deterring and ultimately ending Russian aggression according to international law and rules.

Conclusions

The greatest existential challenge in the world since the Second World War has been the full-scale war unleashed against the Ukrainian people. It clearly demonstrated the cost of true independence, sovereignty, commitment to freedom and democracy measured in tens and hundreds of thousands of lost and mutilated human lives and personal tragedies. The Russian state is unchanged in its nature which is a continuation of the acquired character of political and economic weakness based on the abuse of natural resources rather than the need for modernization. It relies on previously approved archaic forms of resolving political issues trying to dictate its own will not only to the Ukrainian people but also to the established European democracies.

Existential confrontations have spread to much larger geographical areas than the Ukrainian territories. They have renewed the humanitarian crisis, updated previously unsolved problems and created the illusion of the permissibility of solving certain problems from the “force” position. Russia’s aggression has once again reminded us of the fragility of democracy in the modern world. It has demonstrated the depth and scale of the humanitarian catastrophe caused by this conventional war and has become a real threat to the sustainable development of Europe and the entire world.

Conflict of interest

The authors state no conflict of interest.

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